

Intracycle Flow Dynamics of Cross-Flow Turbine Optimization

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Cross-flow turbines (CFT) comprise an important type of marine energy converter for fast-moving water currents. Distinct from the more common axial flow turbines, their axis of rotation is perpendicular to the freestream velocity. This feature allows for omnidirectional operation and high blockage implementation. Previous research has investigated CFT dynamics, both experimentally and through computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models, but most of this work utilizes a constant rotation rate to understand performance. There are several optimization strategies explored in both experimental and numerical research to improve power generation of a turbine within each cycle. Some of these include confinement exploitation, pitch control, intracycle velocity control, and turbine-turbine interactions. All of these strategies alter the relative blade velocity at key points in the cycle to improve power generation.

One current project along these lines aims to exploit confinement within river and tidal channels to improve performance of CFT arrays. Through this design and control optimization process, significant improvements in efficiency and lower costs of energy can be achieved. In addition, turbines in close proximity, such as two side-by-side counter-rotating turbines, can increase power output due to local blockage from turbine-to-turbine interactions. In separate investigations, the performance of a single turbine undergoing intracycle angular velocity control has also shown improvements to efficiency. Termed “intracycle control”, this strategy modulates the angular velocity of the turbine as a function of phase. In unconfined or low blockage scenarios, this control changes blade velocity periodically to cause local cyclic flow speed changes similar to those seen due to high confinement and blockage.

Experimentally, it has been shown that the combination of confinement and intracycle control do not yield stackable efficiency improvements. To explain this phenomenon, we use simulations to investigate and uncover the specific changes in blade dynamics for the separate cases of confinement and intracycle control, each of which lead to improved power generation over the turbine cycle when the strategy is employed in isolation. Our simulations show that shifts in blade relative velocity and timing of vortex shedding, influenced by confinement and intracycle control, significantly impact CFT power and recovery cycles. This investigation will be able to quantitatively explain changes to flow dynamics and expose blade-level effects of combining multiple optimization strategies.